

EM amplification of microwave phonons in nonlinear resonant microcavities

D. Mencarelli, M. Stocchi, L. Pierantoni

Abstract— In this contribution, we report on numerical simulation of a multi-physic Electromagnetic/Mechanical problem, as a further step towards the development of GHz circuits based on phonon propagation at micro-and nano-scale. In the future, this kind of circuits is likely to integrate opto-mechanically pumped phonon sources and detectors, as well as phonon processing components (waveguides, splitters, memories) to process information by means of phonons. In particular, we propose a rigorous approach for the solution of the EM/mechanical system of equations governing light behavior in opto-mechanical cavities, with the help of the Transformation Optics (TO) method. Such kind of calculation allows the development of an efficient generation of GHz to tens of GHz coherent phonon sources, by engineering their propagation or coupling with phonon waveguides.

I. INTRODUCTION

The interplay of mechanical vibrational modes and confined electromagnetic fields in opto-mechanical (OM) cavities constitutes a challenging problem, from the simulation point of view, due to its intrinsic nonlinear and multiscale nature. This complexity can lead to unexpected and useful, even nonlinear, effects [1,2]. In the last years, the emerging field of OM cavities has brought about several breakthroughs that would enable on-chip photonic-operated phononic circuits to become a reality [3-5]. In particular, optically-driven sources of coherent phonons, phonon lasers albeit at low temperatures, have been demonstrated up to a few GHz. Such frequency range allows straightforward manipulation of radio frequency (RF) signals, otherwise not easily attainable by electrical means with, e.g., interdigitated transducers (IDT).

In this work, microwave phonons have the form of surface acoustic waves (SAW), already object of intense study for sensing or filtering applications [20-24]. An important advantage of SAW-based devices originates from the wavelength of the relevant phonons (tens to 100s nm at 300 K), which can lead to significant down-scaling. Moreover, compared to pure nano electromechanical actuation, the OM approach does not suffer from capacitive nor impedance mismatch issues. In this framework, nonlinear opto-mechanical interaction is being intensively investigated, with a view to advanced device modulation [18, 19].

The above kind of research is highly interdisciplinary, moving along the frontier of many fields, i.e. optics, photonics and electronics, and at the boundary between nanophysics and quantum optics. In particular, some recent achievements of opto-mechanical ground state cooling [12, 13] promise coherent control of the quantum motion of mechanical resonators.

The analytical treatment of micro- and nano-OM cavities relies on the coupling between the two ruling equations of, respectively, the continuum mechanics and the electromagnetism [6]. To address this problem, we apply the Transformation Optics (TO) technique, which relies on invariance of Maxwell's equations under coordinate transformation. Such coordinate transformation turns into a change of the material parameters, i.e. permittivity and permeability, which can become anisotropic and inhomogeneous. The success of TO resides in the theoretical and practical advancements of metamaterial research, as, in fact, the choice of metamaterials offers important degrees of freedom in the material parameters. An interesting extension of TO, useful for opto-mechanical applications, has been recently suggested in [7], where time harmonic variation of the coordinate transformation is accounted for. In particular, the coordinate transformations are varying at the mechanical frequency, and enter Maxwell's equations after proper matching of the harmonics having the same time dependence, as will be made clearer in section II. Such approach is applied here, for the first time, to the case of opto-mechanical cavities: relevant numerical examples, independent theory-experiment comparison, and related discussion, are provided in section III, so as to largely expand and substantially extend the work presented at the IMWS-AMP conference [25].

II. THEORETICAL BASIS

A mechanical wave, propagating in a generic medium, can be described in terms of a three-dimensional displacement \mathbf{u} satisfying the continuum-mechanical equations of motion in a Lagrangian coordinate system:

$$\rho_0 \Omega^2 \mathbf{u} + \nabla_X \cdot (\bar{\bar{F}} \bar{\bar{S}}) = -\mathbf{F}_{RP} - \mathbf{F}_{ES,V} - \mathbf{F}_{ES,B} \quad (1)$$

D. Mencarelli is with the University Politecnica of Marche, Via Brecce Bianche 1, 60100, Ancona, and National Institute of Nuclear Physics, INFN-LNF, Frascati, Rome, Italy (corresponding author, phone: +39 3406847560; e-mail: d.mencarelli@univpm.it).

M. Stocchi is with the University Politecnica of Marche, Via Brecce Bianche 1, 60100, Ancona, Italy (e-mail: m.stocchi@pm.univpm.it).

L. Pierantoni is with the University Politecnica of Marche, Via Brecce Bianche 1, 60100, Ancona, and National Institute of Nuclear Physics, INFN-LNF, Frascati, Rome, Italy (e-mail: l.pierantoni@univpm.it).

where $\bar{\bar{F}}$ indicates the deformation gradient tensor, ρ_0 is the mass density of the undeformed configuration, Ω is the acoustic wave frequency, \bar{S} is the second Piola-Kirchhoff tensor, and $\nabla_{\mathbf{X}}$ represents the nabla operator in Lagrangian coordinates. The right-hand side of Eq. (1) describes how the linear momentum is modified by the presence of an EM-field, through volume and boundary electrostrictive forces ($\mathbf{F}_{ES,V}$ and $\mathbf{F}_{ES,V}$ respectively), and through radiation pressure boundary force (\mathbf{F}_{RP}), all related to the E-field components:

$$\mathbf{F}_{ES,V} = f_x^{ES,V} \hat{x} + f_y^{ES,V} \hat{y} + f_z^{ES,V} \hat{z} \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{F}_{RP} = & -\frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_0 E_{t1} E_{t2}^* (\varepsilon_2 - \varepsilon_1) \mathbf{n} + \\ & + \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_0^{-1} D_{1n}^2 (\varepsilon_2^{-1} - \varepsilon_1^{-1}) \mathbf{n} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{ES,B} = (\sigma_{1ij} - \sigma_{2ij}) \mathbf{n}_j \quad (4)$$

The individual force contributions appearing in the right hand side of eq. (2) are given by

$$f_x^{ES,V} = -\partial_x \sigma_{xx} - \partial_y \sigma_{xy} - \partial_z \sigma_{xz},$$

$$f_y^{ES,V} = -\partial_x \sigma_{xy} - \partial_y \sigma_{yy} - \partial_z \sigma_{yz},$$

$$f_z^{ES,V} = -\partial_x \sigma_{xz} - \partial_y \sigma_{yz} - \partial_z \sigma_{zz}$$

where the components of the electrostriction tensor $\bar{\sigma}$ of the cavity material are defined as

$$\sigma_{ij} = -\frac{1}{2} \varepsilon^2 p_{ijkl} E_k E_l \quad (5)$$

which includes the strain-optical tensor p_{ijkl} .

For silicon, a cubic crystal is assumed with point symmetry group m3m, with the x-axis and y-axis respectively aligned to the $\frac{1}{2}100$ and $\frac{1}{2}010$ crystal, it is (p11;p12;p44)=(0:094;0:017;0:051). The above force terms oscillate at the angular frequency Ω , depending on the frequencies ω_1 and ω_2 of the pump and of the scattered E-field, respectively. In particular, the assumption

$$\omega_2 = \omega_1 - \Omega \quad (6)$$

is made to ensure consistency with the synchronization selection rule. In the following, we indicate by ε_1 as the dielectric constant of the cavity, and by ε_2 the dielectric constant of the surrounding domain.

Once clarified the effect of the EM field on the mechanical wave equation, let us consider the effect produced by the mechanical wave on Maxwell's equations: a photo-elastic perturbation is added to the relative permittivity, with the following expression

$$\bar{\Delta \varepsilon_r} = -\sum_{kl} \varepsilon_r^2 p_{ijkl} \epsilon_{kl} \quad (7)$$

where ϵ_{kl} is the strain tensor, directly related to the displacement \mathbf{u} oscillating at the mechanical frequency Ω .

In the following, Maxwell's equations are written for a pump probe configuration, with two monochromatic EM fields \mathbf{E}_1 and \mathbf{E}_2 acting as pump and probe respectively. Using Eq. (7), we introduce the mechanical perturbation of the polarization \mathbf{P}_i

$$\nabla^2 \mathbf{E}_1 = -\mu \omega_1^2 \mathbf{P}_1 = -\mu \omega_1^2 \frac{\varepsilon_0}{2} \bar{\Delta \varepsilon_r} \mathbf{E}_2 \quad (8)$$

$$\nabla^2 \mathbf{E}_2 = -\mu \omega_2^2 \mathbf{P}_2 = -\mu \omega_2^2 \frac{\varepsilon_0}{2} \bar{\Delta \varepsilon_r}^* \mathbf{E}_1 \quad (9)$$

In the particular case where simple EM plane waves are involved, from Eq. (8) and Eq. (9) the usual phase matching condition follows as

$$\mathbf{k}_m = \mathbf{k}_1 - \mathbf{k}_2 \quad (10)$$

where \mathbf{k}_1 , \mathbf{k}_2 and \mathbf{k}_m are the wave numbers of pump, probe and mechanical waves, respectively.

The opto-mechanical coupling process, expressed by (1), (8), (9), although analytically straightforward, requires further processing before implementation in a full-wave solver. That is because the Eulerian environment in which the Helmholtz equations are solved is not able to account for the moving geometry, arising from the displacements. As a matter of fact, the latter can be numerically significant in case of micro- and nano-scale cavities. Transformation Optics (TO) can be of help in addressing the above problem, as recently reported in the literature [7]. The harmonic version of TO method models the movement of the material points of the computation domain as a time-oscillation of the electromagnetic parameters μ and ε :

$$\bar{\varepsilon} = \frac{\bar{\bar{F}} \bar{\bar{F}}^T}{\det \bar{\bar{F}}} \varepsilon = \bar{g} \varepsilon, \quad \bar{\mu} = \frac{\bar{\bar{F}} \bar{\bar{F}}^T}{\det \bar{\bar{F}}} \mu = \bar{g} \mu \quad (10)$$

In (10), the deformation gradient $\bar{\bar{F}}$ of standard TO represents the Jacobian matrix associated to the coordinate transformation, whereas \bar{g} is the corresponding metric tensor, which is conveniently expressed as a linear combination of its spectral harmonics, multiple of the mechanical frequency:

$$\bar{g} = \sum_{n=-3}^3 \bar{g}_n e^{in\Omega t}$$

Considering an isotropic medium, the Maxwell's equations are then rewritten in the following synoptic form:

$$\begin{aligned} -\nabla \times \tilde{\mathbf{E}} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\bar{g} \mu \tilde{\mathbf{H}}) \\ \nabla \times \tilde{\mathbf{H}} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial t} [\bar{g} (\varepsilon + \varepsilon_0 \bar{\Delta \varepsilon_r}) \tilde{\mathbf{E}}] + \bar{g} \sigma_e \tilde{\mathbf{E}} \end{aligned}$$

By taking curls and separating harmonics, we get the wave equations [8]:

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \times \bar{A}^{-1} \nabla \times \mathbf{E}_1 - \omega_1^2 \bar{C} \mathbf{E}_1 &= \omega_1^2 [\bar{K} \mathbf{E}_1 + (\bar{D} + \bar{L}) \mathbf{E}_2] - \\ i \omega_1 \nabla \times (\bar{A}^{-1} \bar{B} \mathbf{H}_2) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

$$\nabla \times \bar{\mathbf{A}}^{-1} \nabla \times \mathbf{E}_2 - \omega_2^2 \bar{\mathbf{C}} \mathbf{E}_2 = \omega_2^2 [(\bar{\mathbf{D}}^* + \bar{\mathbf{L}}^*) \mathbf{E}_1 + \bar{\mathbf{K}} \mathbf{E}_2] - i\omega_2 \nabla \times (\bar{\mathbf{A}}^{-1} \bar{\mathbf{B}}^* \mathbf{H}_1) \quad (12)$$

where

$$\bar{\mathbf{A}} = \bar{g}_0 \boldsymbol{\mu}, \quad \bar{\mathbf{B}} = \bar{g}_1 \boldsymbol{\mu}, \quad \bar{\mathbf{C}} = \bar{g}_0 \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, \quad \bar{\mathbf{D}} = \bar{g}_1 \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, \quad \bar{\mathbf{K}} = \frac{\varepsilon_0}{2} (\bar{g}_1 \bar{\Delta} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^* + \bar{g}_1^* \bar{\Delta} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) \text{ and } \bar{\mathbf{L}} = \frac{\varepsilon_0}{2} (\bar{g}_2 \bar{\Delta} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^* + \bar{g}_2 \bar{\Delta} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}).$$

At this point, it is possible to recognize that the matrix $\bar{\mathbf{A}}$ plays the role of $\bar{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_r$, and $\omega_n^2 \bar{\mathbf{C}}$ that of $k_0^2 [\bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_r - i\sigma_e/(\omega \varepsilon_0)]$, in the standard linear wave equation. Finally, the terms on the right hand side of Eq. (11) and Eq. (12) play the role of distributed and field-dependent sources.

The key enabling factor for phonon lasing (cooling) is provided by the forward (backward) BS occurring in the considered OM cavity. In particular, BS has to produce a displacement from the equilibrium position for the involved mechanical mode, comparable with that taking place at thermal equilibrium, without external excitation. The latter can be estimated, taking into account phonon occupation, for the considered temperature, given in [2, 9]:

$$u = \frac{4k_B T}{m_{\text{eff}} \Omega^2}$$

It is evident from the above expression that the effective mass plays an important role in opto-mechanical phenomena, since, the lower the mass, the larger is the thermal displacement, for the considered mechanical frequency. It is also expected that a lower effective mass corresponds to a higher mechanical displacement induced by the e.m. action. A numerical estimation of the effective mass of a resonator mode can be derived, from its potential energy [10], as:

$$m_{\text{eff}} = \int \rho |\mathbf{u}|^2 dV$$

where ρ is the material local density and \mathbf{u} is made adimensional by means of normalization to its peak value.

It is important to remark that in a linear model the effective mass is intrinsically related only to the geometry and to the physical parameters of the material forming the resonant cavity, but not to its electromagnetic response.

In all simulation presented here, the medium is assumed to have mechanical losses at high frequency (5-6 GHz). Consequently, an isotropic loss factor $\xi = 10^{-3}$ is assigned to all vibrational modes, which arbitrarily accounts for the various loss mechanisms [14]. Introducing this loss flattens down to 1000 the mechanical Q factor of the mode considered in this work (see Fig 2(c)). In fact, high frequency may enhance mechanical losses, which typically grow with the square of the frequency. As in [7], the above factor ξ results in a viscosity tensor whose non-vanishing elements are given by the corresponding stiffness tensor elements scaled down by $1/\xi$.

III. NUMERICAL RESULTS

A. Single OM cavity.

In order to test the numerical consistence of our approach, we provide simulation examples and compare results with the experimental ones. We consider, as a first example, a silicon OM resonant cavity with geometry similar to that of [11]: the mechanical and optical dispersion curves of the Si beam in- and out-of-the-cavity regions show, respectively, allowed and forbidden (bandgap) propagation, both for optical and mechanical modes, thus providing the possibility for highly confined modes, with high quality factors. Differently from [11], the optical structure has tapered holes at the beginning and at the end of the hole-array, to facilitate numerical excitation from either sides of the Si beam, namely pump excitation from left, and probe excitation from the right of the cavity. We assume, from (6), the frequency of the probe equal to the resonant frequency ($\omega_2/2\pi = F_O$) of the cavity, whereas the pump frequency is given by ($\omega_1/2\pi = F_O + \Omega/2\pi$), where Ω is the mechanical-mode resonant frequency.

The Si OM cavity considered in this work, its optical transfer function, and the mechanical spectrum of resonances around an Ω of 5 GHz, with their related parameters of interest, i.e. the Q-factor and the effective mass m_{eff} , are reported in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. (a) OM cavity fabricated on a suspended Si beam; (b) optical scattering parameters through the cavity, (c) spectrum of mechanical-mode resonances around 5 GHz, and corresponding effective masses.

Table I

$\Omega/2\pi$	F_O	I_{Pump}	I_{Probe}	Q_M	Q_O
---------------	-------	-------------------	--------------------	-------	-------

5.67E9 [GHz]	191.549 [THz]	30 μ W	1 μ W	10^3	$\approx 0.5 \cdot 10^5$
-----------------	------------------	---------------	--------------	--------	--------------------------

Table I reports the input pump and probe powers, i.e. I_{pump} and I_{probe} respectively, and summarizes the main cavity parameters, for the simulated optical and mechanical modes, i.e. resonant frequencies and corresponding quality factors Q_O and Q_M . For the chosen mechanical mode, we obtain the strongest OM coupling. Numerical results are reported in Fig. 2: we performed self-consistent simulation of the EM field and mechanical displacement throughout the OM structure. Only the electric field associated to the probe signal is reported, because the pump signal, being much larger, is not significantly affected by OM interaction (un-depleted pump condition).

Fig. 2. The pictures show: (a) electromagnetic field distribution of the probe signal, (b) magnitude of mechanical displacement \mathbf{u} . Pump and probe input powers are assumed as in Table I.

Let also consider the mechanical forces involved in the above opto-mechanical process. The electrostrictive bulk force density $\mathbf{F}_{ES,V}$ associated to a TE y -polarized mode resonating in the cavity (see Fig. 3(a)) is reported in Fig. 4(a). For completeness, the boundary forces $\mathbf{F}_{ES,VB}$ and \mathbf{F}_{RP} , associated to the same resonant mode, have been also reported, respectively in Fig. 3(b) and Fig. 3(c). It can be noted that the largest electrostrictive force values occur in correspondence of dielectric discontinuities.

Fig. 3. Source terms of the mechanical equation (1), assuming the parameters of Table I: (a) electrostriction contributes in the surface boundaries $\mathbf{F}_{ES,B}$ (Pa), (b) radiation pressure \mathbf{F}_{RP} (Pa), (c) electrostriction contributes in the volume $\mathbf{F}_{ES,V}$ (N/m^3).

B. Double OM cavity.

In the following example, let us consider two optically coupled cavities, with possibly different, geometry controlled, coupling rates. The degeneracy of the optical resonance of the individual cavities is broken by the mutual coupling when the spatial distance between the cavities is reduced: two distinct optical resonances are obtained, corresponding to the two frequencies of the nondegenerate resonances. For numerical purposes, different resonance separations are determined by changing the distance between cavities. The proper distance is set by matching the optical frequency separation to the resonant frequency of a specific mechanical mode, as stated under Eq. (6). In a backward SBS configuration, the higher of the two nondegenerate frequencies is populated by the pump field, and the lower frequency gets populated as long as stimulated scattering is effectively mediated by phonon amplification. Its effectiveness depends on several factors, namely, the mechanical effective mass, the spatial overlap between the optical beating signal and the mechanical field, as well as their overall coupling over the cavity, which generalizes the relation (10) for plane waves.

Figure 4 reports the double OM-cavity and related scattering parameters. As a matter of fact, the degeneracies of the mechanical resonant frequencies are only slightly, not significantly, broken. F_M appears to be slightly shifted up in frequency with respect to the single OM-cavity, since the holes have been slightly reshaped, in order to ensure the same quality factor of the single OM-cavity section A . Indeed, the aim of the simulations here is to compare the OM effects in the present case of a double cavity, with those of a single cavity, under same conditions in terms of optical and mechanical quality factors.

Fig. 4. (a) OM cavity made of two cascaded cavities similar to the cavity simulated in section A. (b) optical scattering parameters through the cavity,

La figura 4(b) andrebbe un po' rimpicciolita (solo la b)

Table II

$\Omega/2\pi$	F_{O1}	F_{O2}	Q_M	$Q_{O1} = Q_{O2}$
5.686 [GHz]	191.0645 [THz]	191.0585 [THz]	10^3	$\approx 0.5 \cdot 10^5$

Table II summarizes the main double-cavity parameters, namely the resonant frequencies of the optical/mechanical modes, and corresponding quality factors. In Fig. 5, we report a comparison between the dependence on the pump power of the perturbation of the transmitted probe signal as a function of the frequency: as expected, the OM effect is more evident for the coupled cavities, as, in this case, a lower pump power yields similar reflection, compared to the case of single cavity.

Fig. 5. Probe signal transmission (S_{12}) as a function of the frequency, for different values of pump power, both for single cavity (triangles,

pump power: [0.01, 0.02, 0.03] mW) and double cavity (circles, pump power: [0.005, 0.01, 0.02] mW).

In correspondence to the resonant frequencies of Fig. 5, the maximum mechanical displacements reach their peak values. Results from single and double cavity are compared in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Maximum value of the mechanical displacement, as a function of the frequency, both for single cavity (triangles, pump power: [0.01, 0.02, 0.03] mW) and double cavity (circles, pump power: [0.005, 0.01, 0.02] mW).

The field contribution in the source terms in Eq. (1) is related to pump and probe signals: having both of these signals resonating, clearly increases the dynamical stress exerted by the light, and the correlated mechanical strain, as confirmed in Fig. 6. In particular, the selection rule $(\omega_1 - \omega_2)/2\pi = F_{O1} - F_{O2} \approx \Omega/2\pi$ (see Table II) may produce a strong amplification mechanism of the OM effect, especially in case of high optical and mechanical quality factors, which can attain much higher values than those considered in this work.

The accuracy of TO has been already shown elsewhere by means of relevant examples [9], verified by us with our method. Further proof of numerical consistency is provided in the following: Fig. 7 show a high correlation between our model results and experimental results of ref. [16]. In particular, the transfer function (demodulated RF spectrum) of the resonant cavity of Fig. 7a, in a range of frequencies close to the resonance, shows the peaks of OM coupling with phonons [16]. These peaks correspond, with a good accordance, to the maxima of relative displacements obtained from the self-consistent electromagnetics and continuous-mechanics simulation based on time-harmonic TO (Fig. 7b). The relative values of the displacements, more than their absolute values, are significant here, as the latter scale with the input pump and probe powers.

REFERENCES

- [1] G. Wang, L. Huang, Y.-C. Lai, and C. Grebogi, “Nonlinear dynamics and quantum entanglement in optomechanical systems”, *Phys. Rev. Letters* 112(11): 110406, 2014.
- [2] G. Bahl, M. Tomes, F. Marquardt, and T. Carmon, “Observation of spontaneous Brillouin cooling”, *Nature Physics*, Vol. 8, March 2012, pp. 203-207.
- [3] R.W. Boyd, “Nonlinear optics”, (Academic Press, 2008) Chap. 9, pp. 429, 3rd Ed.
- [4] M. Eichenfield et al., Optomechanical crystals, *Nature* 462, 7269, 2009, pp. 78-82.
- [5] T. Kippenberg et al., “Analysis of Radiation-Pressure Induced Mechanical Oscillation of an Optical Microcavity”, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 95, 2005, pp. 033901-4.
- [6] A. J. Ward and J. B. Pendry, “Refraction and geometry in Maxwell's equations”, *J. Mod. Opt.* 43, 773, 1996.
- [7] R. Zecca, P. T. Bowen, D. R. Smith, S. Larouche, “Transformation-optics simulation method for stimulated Brillouin scattering”, *Phys. Rev. A* 94, 063818, 2016.
- [8] M. Aspelmeyer, T. Kippenberg and F. Marquardt, “Cavity Optomechanics”, *Rev. Mod. Phys.* 86, 1391, 2014.
- [9] Charles Kittel. *Introduction to Solid State Physics*. Wiley, 8 edition, 2004.
- [10] B. D. Hauer, C. Doolin, K.S.D. Beach, and J.P. Davis, A general procedure for thermomechanical calibration of nano/micro-mechanical resonators *Annals of Physics* 339, 181, 2013.
- [11] J. Chan, A. H. Safavi-Naeini, J. T. Hill, S. Meenehan, and O. Painter, “Optimized optomechanical crystal cavity with acoustic radiation shield”, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 101, 081115, 2012.
- [12] A. D. O’Connell, M. Hofheinz, M. Ansmann, Radoslaw C. Bialczak, M. Lenander, Erik Lucero, M. Neeley, D. Sank, H. Wang, M. Weides, J. Wenner, John M. Martinis & A. N. Cleland, “Quantum ground state and single-phonon control of a mechanical resonator”, *Nature* 464, 697-703, 1 April 2010.
- [13] Yu-Long Liu and Yu-xi Liu, “Energy-localization-enhanced ground-state cooling of a mechanical resonator from room temperature in optomechanics using a gain cavity”, *Phys. Rev. A* 96, 023812, 7 August 2017.
- [14] S. Reid, G. Cagnoli, D.R.M. Crooks, J. Hough, P. Murray, S. Rowan, M.M. Fejer, R. Route, S. Zappe, “Mechanical Dissipation in Silicon Flexures”, *2nd Texas Symposium on Relativistic Astrophysics at Stanford University, Dec. 13-17, 2004*.
- [15] Y. A. V. Espinel, F. G. S. Santos, G. O. Luiz, T. P. Mayer Alegre, and G. S. Wiederhecker, *Brillouin Optomechanics in Coupled Silicon Microcavities*, *Sci. Rep.* 7, 43423, 2017.
- [16] D. Navarro-Urrios, J. Gomis-Bresco, S. El-Jallal, M. Oudich, A. Pitanti, N. Capuj, A. Tredicucci, F. Alzina, A. Griol, Y. Pennec, B. Djafari-Rouhani, A. Martínez, and C. M. Sotomayor Torres, “Dynamical back-action at 5.5 GHz in a corrugated optomechanical beam”, *AIP Advances* 4, 124601, 2014.
- [17] Mani Hossein-Zadeh and Kerry J. Vahala, “Observation of optical spring effect in a microtoroidal optomechanical resonator”, *Optics Letters* Vol. 32, Issue 12, pp. 1611-1613, 2007.
- [18] Yaoxian Zheng, Quanqiang Yu, Keyu Tao, and Zhengbiao Ouyang, “All-optical tunable filters based on optomechanical effects in two-dimensional photonic crystal cavities”, *Optics Letters*, Vol. 38, Issue 21, pp. 4362-4365, 2013.
- [19] Rahul Kishor; Yuanjin Zheng, Surface acoustic wave RF sensing and actuation for lab-on-a-chip platforms, *IEEE MTT-S International Microwave Workshop Series on Advanced Materials and Processes for RF and THz Applications (IMWS-AMP)*, pages: 1-4, 2016.
- [20] Jinhong Guo; Yu Chen; Yuejun Kang, RF-activated surface standing acoustic wave for on-chip controllably aligning of bio-

Fig. 7 – Comparison with experimental results. (a) OM cavity, from ref. [16], considered for independent numerical check. (b) Scattered peak powers (blue curve) through the cavity, overlapped with the magnitudes of mechanical displacements (red curve) calculated by time-harmonic TO.

The present work, rather than a mere computational report, is intended to be a step forward towards the full-wave simulation of SBS in coupled OM cavities with high Qs. Typically, the SBS is due to the interaction of travelling waves, like in waveguides, or in structures where waves can freely propagate, such as azimuthally traveling waves in micro-disks [15]. In this study, optical/mechanical modes are localized, but still travelling along the photonic/phononic crystal forming the OM cavity. Thus, the above modes can lead to SBS effect, by travelling back and forth in the cavity after multiple reflections (like in simple Fabry-Pérot) [16]. The underlying physicals is not different from micro-disk or related structures, and the mathematical treatment can be unified thanks to TO.

In general, the present approach is thought to include the effect of i) moving boundaries ii) multimodal optical/mechanical propagation, and iii) spatial transients.. However, extremely high quality factors may pose numerical issues due to the fact that the intrinsic nonlinear character of the problem may be strongly emphasized. Such numerical limits are the object of current work.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this contribution, we reported full-wave modeling of coupled opto-mechanical (OM) cavities, by the application of transformation optics (TO), extended to time-varying mesh deformation at few GHz frequencies. OM coupling in micro- and nano-cavities could help in developing new microwave-photonic devices with extremely small foot-print, sub-mW power consumption, and tunable frequency. We propose some simulation examples to show the joint effect of high-quality mechanical (GHz) and EM (Infrared) resonances, that strongly enhance non-linearity, and make the calculation challenging, but still numerically manageable.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research is supported by the European Project All-Phononic circuits Enabled by Opto-mechanics PHENOMEN, H2020 FETOPEN 2014-2015-RIA, n.713450.

microparticles, IEEE MTT-S International Microwave Workshop Series on RF and Wireless Technologies for Biomedical and Healthcare Applications (IMWS-BIO), pp. 1–3, 2013.

[22] Vladimir D. Kuptsov, Noise factor optimization of surface acoustic wave filters, IEEE MTT-S International Conference on Numerical Electromagnetic and Multiphysics Modeling and Optimization for RF, Microwave, and Terahertz Applications (NEMO), pp. 76–78, 2017.

[23] Takaki Murata; Michio Kadota; Takeshi Nakao; Kenji Matsuda, Surface acoustic wave filter in high frequency with narrow bandwidth and excellent temperature characteristic, IEEE MTT-S International Microwave Symposium Digest, pp. 1255-58, 2008.

[24] Michio Kadota; Takeshi Nakao; Kenji Nishiyama; Shunsuke Kido; Masanori Kato; Ryoichi Omote; Hiroshi Yonekura; Norihiko Takada; Ryoichi Kita; Yasuharu Nakai; Daisuke Yamamoto, Miniature surface acoustic wave devices with excellent temperature stability using high density metal electrodes and SiO₂ film, IEEE MTT-S International Microwave Symposium, pp. 847–50, 2008.

[25] D. Mencarelli, M. Stocchi, L. Pierantoni, A multi-physics approach for the analysis and design of opto-mechanical cavities, IEEE MTT-s International Microwave Workshop Series on Advanced Materials and Processes (IMWS-AMP), Sept. 20-22 2017, Pavia, Italy.